

ABSTRACT

Title: Teachers Experiences of Work Place Violence and Harassment committed by learners in secondary schools in Yaounde VII

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Background: The school is the work place for the teacher. Unfortunately, school violence against teachers is a growing concern globally, affecting not only the safety and well-being of educators but also the overall educational environment.

General Objective: This study investigates the prevalence of various forms of violence experienced by teachers in secondary schools within the Yaounde VII subdivision and examines its impact on their professional well-being and attrition intentions.

Methods: This cross-sectional descriptive study was conducted from March to September 2024, with data collection occurring between June and August 2024. The study population consisted of full-time secondary school teachers with at least 12 months of in-person teaching experience. A sample size of 385 participants was calculated using Andrew Fisher's formula. A self-administered pre-tested questionnaire was used to gather data on experiences of violence, teacher well-being, and thoughts about attrition. Descriptive statistics, chi-square tests, Student's t-tests, and hierarchical multiple linear regression analyses were employed for data analysis, with a significance level set at $p < 0.05$.

Results: A total of 294 teachers participated in the study, with a majority being female (62.9%) and aged between 21-30 years (69.4%). Psychosocial violence was the most commonly reported, with 76.9% of teachers witnessing such incidents. Sexual violence was reported by 33%, while 52% experienced physical violence. Despite these challenges, 67.3% of teachers felt they were effective in their roles, and 62.5% reported a sense of belonging and safety at their schools.

However, 15% considered changing schools, and 13.3% contemplated early retirement due to violence.

Conclusions: The study highlights a significant prevalence of violence against teachers in Yaounde VII, impacting their professional well-being and retention. While many teachers show resilience, a notable minority is at risk of burnout and attrition. Addressing this issue requires comprehensive strategies from the Ministry of Education and other stakeholders to ensure a safer and more supportive school environment.